

A COMPARISON OF PHYSICAL FITNESS LEVELS AND BODY MASS INDEX IN STUDENTS FROM 5TH TO 9TH GRADE IN PHYSICAL EDUCATION CLASSES DEPENDING ON URBAN OR RURAL PLACE OF RESIDENCE

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Abstract

Introduction: The main purpose of this study was to compare the physical fitness levels and body mass index of students from urban and rural residences at an elementary school in Portugal.

Methods: The sample covered 270 students, 142 male and 128 female, aged between 9 and 16, from the 5th to the 9th grade. The Fitnessgram test battery (NES, 2002) measured the physical fitness, the body mass index was based on reference values from the World Health Organization (1995) and the students' profiles were assessed through biographical archives provided by the school. **Results:** The test results only demonstrated significant differences ($p < 0.05$) amongst these students: Females in the 5th and 6th grade in the following tests, trunk extension with better results in students from rural residences and middle strength, with better results in students from urban residences; Males in the 5th and 6th grade in the following tests: the shuttle run with better results in students from rural residences; Females between 7th and 9th grade in the following tests: trunk extension with better results in students from urban residences. **Conclusions:** Significant differences were not observed between the levels of physical fitness and BMI related to the place of residence (rural and urban).

Key words: Physical fitness, BMI, Children, Adolescents, Physical Education, Rural, Urban.

Introduction

In recent decades we have witnessed profound changes in the daily lives of children and adolescents. This seems to be associated with an increasing urbanization, sedentary lifestyles and consequently problems related to health and well-being, including an increase in obesity (Ewing, 1982 cited by Rodrigues Bezerra & Scott, 2005) and the decline in physical fitness levels of children and young people (Kuntzleman, 1992). According to Ezzati et al. (2005, cited in Machado-Rodrigues et al., 2012), urbanization refers to the concentration of people in towns and cities, linked to economic transformation, migration and behavioural changes.

In Portugal about 45% of the population lives in metropolitan areas such as Porto and Lisbon (Baker, 2000). At the same time it is one of the European countries with the highest prevalence of overweight children or children suffering from obesity (Campos et al, s/d; Queiroz (2006).

Regarding these statistics, as stated by Barreto (2000), social inequalities between rural communities have also become increasingly evident, specifically with regard to health resources and education. According to Muula (2007), the interest in health issues in rural areas has increased in recent years, especially when compared to urban communities. Thus, urbanization is a determinant and influential factor for physical activity, sedentary behaviours,

overweight and cardio-respiratory capacity. Intuitively it is assumed that young people living in urban centres are less active than their counterparts, which consequently gives lower levels of cardio-respiratory fitness, such as overweight and obesity levels (Springer et al, 2006; Liu et al. (2008).

However, Rodrigues Bezerra and Scott (2005) analyzed the patterns of physical fitness among boys (7 to 10 years) from urban and rural areas and found that, regardless of environment, similar improvements occurred over the years. However, this differs according to the environment and the type of physical fitness indicator. Boys from rural areas, for example, performed higher in the shuttle run test and the boys from urban areas performed higher in the test of horizontal jump.

Seeking to establish a relationship between the periods of physical activity and inactivity and the environment (rural or urban) in which young people live, the study of Bathrellou, Lazarou, Panagiotakos and Sidossis (2007), which included a sample of 1,140 children from rural and urban areas in Cyprus found that children from rural areas are slightly more active after school and busy with outdoor tasks compared to children from an urban environment. However, children from urban areas are more inclined to the practice of weekly sport in comparison with their peers from rural areas. These data suggest that the distribution of children in relation to physical activity and inactivity is similar between urban and rural areas: the researchers found no significant differences in physical activity habits and sedentary behaviour among children in rural and urban areas of Cyprus.

Still reviewing the periods of physical activity and inactivity, as well as the cardio-respiratory fitness of young people from urban and rural areas, the study of Coelho and Silva et al. (2012) found that urban adolescents, of both sexes, spend less time in sedentary activities than rural adolescents. Thus, the study found that the area of residence was related to fitness, time spent in sedentary behaviors and cardio-respiratory fitness among young people, and that interventions seeking to improve health and active lifestyles in youth should consider the socio-geographic impact factor.

As we found in our studies, investigations concerning this issue have not been completely concordant (Cicagnami, 2008). This appears from the outset because there is no consensus on the definitions of urban and rural areas, as well as the impact this uncertainty has on the sample (students residing in rural and urban areas) and the consequent creation of groups to study. This means that when counting students in certain groups who really should not belong to such groups, we may incur a sample selection error, and this in turn affects the internal validity of our study. In this situation, the results cannot be generalized, so our study would lose the possibility of having a coherent and credible external validity.

With regard to the replication of the results obtained in existing studies for different geographical areas, we can assume that this will be limited to the characteristics of the studied context, affecting their representativeness, i.e., its external validity.

In this study, our purpose is to analyze the levels of physical fitness and obesity in students of a school in the North Interior of Portugal, whose geographical location generally allows the coexistence of students from different areas of residence within the district in which it operates. Indeed, in this study we intend to compare the levels of physical fitness and obesity at different ages and for both genders, as well as their variability depending on area of residence (urban and rural).

Methods

Sample

The population study was composed of children and adolescents attending an elementary school in Guarda district. Initially authorization to carry out the data collection was requested in person and in writing to the School Director through the Pedagogical Council, together with information concerning the objectives for the study. On the basis of this, the school board approved the research. The sample was studied according to gender, grade, and the place of residence of the subjects. Inclusion criteria were the attendance of the 2nd and 3rd cycle of education (from 5th to 9th grade) of an elementary school. We assume as sample exclusion criteria physical disability for

physical activity and identification of special educational needs, so that there are no misrepresentations of the data collected by the objective of this study. The total number of participants was 270 students, representing 86% of the total school population which was 314 students. These students were aged between 9 and 16 years of age, and in the 3rd cycle of education 83 were male (45 in urban residence

and 38 with rural residence) and 80 were female (51 in urban residence and 29 with rural residence). Regarding students from 5th to 6th grade 59 students were male (41 in urban residence and 18 in rural residence) and 48 were female (28 in urban residence and 20 in rural residence). These data were collected directly from the constant biographical record of the class.

Table I. Frequency and percentage of students according to grade, gender and residence context

Grade	Gender	Residence	Frequency	Students %
5 th and 6 th grade	Male	Urban	41	15.2%
		Rural	18	6.7%
	Female	Urban	28	10.4%
		Rural	20	7.4%
7 th to 9 th grade	Male	Urban	45	16.7%
		Rural	38	14.1%
	Female	Urban	51	18.9%
		Rural	29	10.7%
Total sample			270	100%

This is a non-probabilistic and intentional sample, because there is a deliberate choice of subjects belonging to the sample and certain characteristics that they possess have been considered.

Instruments

The data collected for the analysis of physical fitness were the values produced by the application of the battery Fitnessgram tests (NES, 2002), since these tests align with familiarity criteria, and can be used over several age levels. Furthermore, these tests offer ease of management, measurement and evaluation of these components of physical fitness with little or no equipment at all. The tests contemplated in this test battery are: the shuttle-run evaluating endurance; abdominal and extension of arms to evaluate middle and upper force; sits-and-reach and trunk extension to assess flexibility, as well as body mass index (BMI) and percentage of body fat (% BF) assessing body composition, calculated by the formula: $BMI = \frac{\text{weight}}{\text{height}^2}$ (meters).

As for the biographical data of the sample participants, these were provided by the

elementary school upon an appropriate written request to the School Director and access to the appropriate direction dossier for each class. Prior to collection of data concerning the research, students were informed about the objectives of this study and that their participation was voluntary and optional.

Procedures

Before any procedures were carried out, informed consent was delivered from the children's parents accepting their participation in this study.

The Shuttle-run test is a test for progressive exertion levels, namely rising from a low intensity and becoming increasingly intensive. The purpose of this is to achieve the maximum distance possible in stages of 20 meter distances, increasing speed successively over one minute. In this regard, a route of 20 meters was initially set with a cone marker and a line at each end. The researchers were always the same throughout the study, prepared with record sheets and pens. These marked the number corresponding to the sequence that the individual completed, and when the sequence was failed

they circled the number corresponding to that exercise.

The test protocol was based on instructing students to complete as many laps as possible, touching the bottom line when they heard a signal. At this point, they were expected to reverse their direction of racing to the other end. Where students reached the line before the signal, they were expected to wait for it before running in the opposite direction. The pace of running was stipulated by a set of acoustic signal intervals between them, produced by a stereo system. The running speed was 8.5 km / h at the start of the test and it was increased by 0.5 km / h every minute. A signal indicating the end time of each route and a triple signal after each minute indicated the end of each level of effort. This last signal was intended to alert students that the race pace would increase, forcing them to accelerate the race to cover the 20 meters in less time. In situations when students did not reach the line at the buzzer they were expected to immediately reverse the direction of the race. The student was then given another opportunity to try to keep pace with the race. The students repeated this procedure until they were no longer able to reach the lines at the sound of the signal. At the end of testing, students continued walking to return to rest. On the test of middle strength, the goal was to achieve the largest number of abdominal push-ups to a maximum of 75, making use of a specific cadence. To achieve this, some test material was needed, including a gym mattress, measuring tape, a CD with cadence and a stereo system.

Two students were necessary for the test run in the class so that one executed it while the other helped. The first assumed the supine position with knees bent, feet flat on the mattress, legs slightly apart and arms extended and in contact with the proximal end of the measuring tape. The second, kneeling, supported the head of their colleague and was responsible for counting and error checking. To complete an abdominal push-up it was necessary to determine if there was a slip of the finger from the proximal end to the distal end of the measurement range. The test was interrupted whenever the performer: (i) Reached the maximum number of repetitions; (ii) Rested

between two executions; or (iii) Stopped the movement and / or performed a second repetition incorrectly, i.e. after the first error or failure in carrying out the movement test it would be completed. In the upper strength test, the student had to maintain the largest number of arm extensions to the sound of a particular cadence. They had to perform arm flexion and extension with no support from any part of the body, so as not to be eliminated. The dynamic test developed in pairs, each pair observing and correcting the position of the other during execution. The student then assumed a prone position on the mattress, placing their hands under their shoulders, fingers extended, legs extended, parallel and slightly apart, leaning on tiptoe. The performer was expected to rise from the mattress using the force of their arms to put them in extension, keeping their back and legs aligned (board). The body should form a straight line from head to toe throughout the test. The performer must then flex the arms to the elbows to form a 90° angle with the arms parallel to the ground. To complete an arm extension it was necessary to determine if the student was bending the arms at a 90° angle and maintaining the plank position. The test was stopped when the thrower (i) reached the maximum number of repetitions; (ii) rested between two executions; or (iii) stopped the movement and / or performed a second repetition incorrectly, i.e. after the first error or failure in performing the movement the test was terminated. On the trunk extension test, the performer positioned themselves in the prone position, supporting the maximum length of their trunk, where the distance between their chin and the ground was measured, with the position of the head neutral. The trunk extension test was performed with the performer positioned in the prone position with legs extended, hands placed under the thighs and the head fixed on an imaginary point. On the evaluator's signal, he or she performed the maximum length of the trunk, with measurements of the distance between the chin of the performer and the ground (position of the head neutral). The elevated position of the trunk was to be maintained for several seconds to provide the reading of the result. Two attempts were allowed and the best result was registered. This test required the use of a slit 50 cm long, a

mattress and a log for recording the results. Body mass index was measured by recording the height and weight of students. The height in cm was determined with a SECA 220 stadiometer in a standing position with feet together and barefoot, arms extended along the trunk, with eyes directed forward, the ear aligned with the shoulder and the back of the body in contact with the ruler. As for weight, students were also barefoot and wearing light clothing, and with the measurement taken from the scales as mentioned above. These measurements had to be carefully considered, so as to choose a time when students had not just finished lunch or ingested large amounts of water (Fragoso and Vieira, 2000). The BMI for being overweight or obese were based on the reference values of the International Obesity Task Force (IOTF, Pediatric Obesity, 2012), by gender and age.

Statistical analysis

Data analysis was performed using SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences, version 21.0 for Windows) aided by a database of values collected in Microsoft Office Excel. Initially we characterized our sample using frequency tables according to grade, gender and residence context. Later we found the data normality using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov or the Shapiro-Wilk test when the sample was higher or lower than 30 subjects respectively. The tests that followed a normal distribution were submitted to inferential analysis to identify differences on the average values, using parametric and nonparametric techniques in accordance with the prior confirmation of normal distribution of data - T-test for independent samples and the Mann-Whitney test respectively. We considered significant differences exist when the $p < .05$.

Table II. Presentation of the mean values, standard deviation and P value of physical fitness tests depending on the residence for females between 5th and 9th grade.

Test	Education Grade	Urban mean	Rural mean	P Value	Standard deviation Urban / Standard deviation Rural
BMI	5 th and 6 th grade	19:20	17.74	.900	4.12 / 2.73
	7 th to 9 th grade	19.95	21:55	.148	2.84 / 4:00
Upper strength	5 th and 6 th grade	10:50	8:00	.167	6.71 / 05:06
	7 th to 9 th grade	22:35	24.41	.182	24.12 / 23:40
Middle strength	5 th and 6 th grade	24.96	18.70	.045	12:41 / 17:00
	7 th to 9 th grade	27.25	28.41	.870	25.10 / 26.52
Trunk extension	5 th and 6 th grade	21.96	24.75	.030	4:29 / 4:18
	7 th to 9 th grade	29.80	27.31	.012	4.88 / 5.86
Sit and reach left.	5 th and 6 th grade	24.36	24:20	.932	6:38 / 6:07
	7 th to 9 th grade	26.63	25.24	.273	5.92 / 8.17
Sit and reach right.	5 th and 6 th grade	24.21	25.15	.506	6.95 / 5.86
	7 th to 9 th grade	25.43	25.38	.850	6:01 / 7.74
Shuttle-run	5 th and 6 th grade	24.93	22.85	.555	12.92 / 10:39
	7 th to 9 th grade	32.75	36.21	.885	9.63 / 17.70

Results

The collected data were studied and grouped according to the grade and gender of the sample participants, depending on their residence (urban or rural environment) and the values obtained in the shuttle-run tests, upper strength, middle strength, sit and reach, trunk extension and body mass index.

Presented in Table II are the average values of physical fitness and BMI tests

depending on the residence of female gender from 5th to 9th grade.

With regards to students of 5th and 6th grade we found that in the results of physical fitness tests, there were no significant differences between students with urban and rural residence, with the exception of the trunk extension test with a P value=.030 and middle strength with a value of P=.045. The trunk extension test among students with rural residence obtained better results, namely 24.75,

compared to 21.96 recorded by students with urban residence. As for the mean strength test, the students with urban residence had an average of 24.96 higher than the average of the students with rural residence which was 18.70. In the group of students from 7th to 9th grade, in general, there are no significant differences in

the results of the physical fitness tests analyzed, except for the trunk extension test that shows us a value of $P=.012$. The students with urban residence had an average of 29.80 which is higher than the average of 27.31 of students with rural residence.

Table III. Presentation of mean values, standard deviation and P value of physical fitness tests depending on residence for male gender.

Test	Education Grade	Urban mean	Rural mean	P Value	Standard deviation Urban / Standard deviation Rural
BMI	5 th and 6 th grade	21:27	17.84	.075	5.84 / 2.95
	7 th to 9 th grade	20:55	20:03	.996	4.23 / 3.57
Upper strength	5 th and 6 th grade	11:32	9:50	.442	5.29 / 7.82
	7 th to 9 th grade	31.07	31.82	.635	23:27 / 20.85
Middle strength	5 th and 6 th grade	25.49	28.50	.114	17:39 / 15.75
	7 th to 9 th grade	41.33	44.26	10:00 am	30.10 / 32.94
Trunk extension	5 th and 6 th grade	23:34	23:17	.373	4:49 / 6:17
	7 th to 9 th grade	28.73	28.47	.812	5.81 / 6:00
Sit and reach left.	5 th and 6 th grade	21:34	21.94	.636	7:05 / 7:47
	7 th to 9 th grade	21:44	21:37	.751	8.82 / 7.66
Sit and reach right.	5 th and 6 th grade	21.61	22:22	.665	8:02 / 6.90
	7 th to 9 th grade	21:44	21:42	.754	9.21 / 7.60
Shuttle-run	5 th and 6 th grade	26.83	36.39	.039	12:46 / 17:39
	7 th to 9 th grade	48.18	53.53	.286	06.19 / 26.43

Presented in Table III are the mean values of physical fitness and BMI tests depending on the place of residence of male subjects.

Regarding the 5th and 6th grade we have found no significant differences in physical fitness tests, with the exception of the shuttle-run test that obtained a value of $P=.039$. In this test students with rural residence registered an average of 36.39 which was higher than the results of students in an urban context, being 26.83.

Between 7th and 9th grade we didn't find any significant differences in all results of physical fitness tests collected.

Discussion

The objective of this investigation was to compare physical fitness levels and BMI of urban and rural students in a school in the North Interior of Portugal. Essentially this study suggests that children residing in urban and rural areas enjoy the same amounts of activity and physical inactivity, since they do not display results with significant differences between them

in most of the tests, considering these same results a consequence of active or sedentary lifestyles. In fact the absence of significant differences in the levels of physical fitness and BMI in most tests among students residing in rural and urban areas seems to be in agreement with the generality of the revised bibliography. The study of Machado-Rodrigues et al. (2012) seeks a connection between physical activity, physical inactivity and sedentary behaviors in relation to cardio-respiratory fitness of 362 adolescents (165 males and 197 females), aged between 13 and 16 living in rural and urban areas of central Portugal. The findings of this study point to the trend among urban students of both genders for expending less time on sedentary activities than rural students, showing that young urban males are more active than rural ones during the weekends. However, with regard to females, urban girls are less active than rural girls during the weekdays. Also, according to the researchers, the rural students of both genders have higher levels of cardio-respiratory fitness than their urban counterparts.

In fact, the time spent by young people in physical or sports related activity can be decisive for the results obtained in the physical fitness tests. As mentioned, our research does not corroborate with the analysis that there is a prevalence of best results for physical fitness among residents in rural or urban areas, because in most tests, no significant differences were identified between the two groups. The only differences relate to the prevalence of better results of urban youth in two tests (middle strength in the females of 5th and 6th grade, and trunk extension in females of 7th to 9th grade) and better results in rural youth in two other tests (shuttle-run in males of 5th and 6th grade and trunk extension in females of 5th and 6th grade), so even in the recorded differences, urban and rural groups are balanced (2 tests each).

Our results are also divergent from Rodrigues, Bezerra and Scott's (2005) study, conducted on the North coast of Portugal, comparing the physical fitness standards of 1,832 urban and rural boys aged between 7 and 10 years. Data from this study showed that urban and rural youth display a level of fitness which differs significantly and over age. The only point in common in relation with our study is the existence of differences in specific tests of physical fitness, specifically the shuttle-run test, middle strength and trunk extension. The divergence does not end in the studies mentioned, since the results of the research carried out by Martins and Honório (2013) - which consisted in the analysis of levels of physical fitness and the degree of association in relation to rural and urban areas of children of 1st to 4th grade in the Fundão district with a sample of 161 students - point to the existence of significant differences both in terms of BMI, or the results of physical fitness tests with higher values for urban children. However, the study carried out by Bathrellou, Lazarou, Panagiotakos and Sidossis (2007), which assessed periods of physical activity and inactivity among 1,140 children in urban and rural areas of Cyprus identify compliance with the data we obtained in the sample of urban and rural students in the North Interior of Portugal. Just as there were no differences between periods of physical activity

and inactivity among Cypriot youth from urban and rural areas, neither does our study point to similar differences based on the results of physical fitness tests pertaining to periods of physical activity. It is important to note that our results should not be generalized to the rest of the Portuguese territory, so they should be examined with due reservation. In future research the inclusion of a socio-economic variable is suggested, which was not taken into consideration in this study and could induce some variability to the data collected. It is also important that the sample was not filtered according to the hypothetical differences in levels of physical activity or in so much as the practice of extra-curricular sports activity. Future studies should consider the influence of these parameters because of how they may have influenced the existence of significant differences in the investigations of Martins and Honório (2013), as well as Rodrigues Bezerra and Scott (2005). They may also have influenced the lack of significant differences in our study since they were not controlled.

Conclusions

The registered results allow us to conclude that significant differences were not observed between the levels of physical fitness and BMI related to the place of residence (rural and urban).

From a practical perspective this study can serve as a document to support this school, as it assists in defining the sports to offer in extracurricular activities (in terms of schedules, types of activities, etc.), identifying the students who lack these kinds of activities, and assessing them in relation to their residence (urban or rural). It is also useful as a tool for promoting political analysis of physical and sports activity in the district of Guarda, as it relates to subjects residing in urban and rural areas.

This is a contribution that can be added to existing literature, enabling the researcher in some way to analyze the differences in the levels of physical fitness and BMI in children and adolescents in the North Interior of Portugal according to their homes, whether urban or rural.

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